

An Overview of the Correlation between Mental Health and Infertility

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Abstract

Infertility is an often neglected struggle that one has to handle alone silently. It is a condition caused due to multiple underlying diseases and disorders. Patients who struggle with infertility have reported harboring a feeling of anxiety, depression, loss of control, and isolation. It is widely known that infertility causes stress, but unclear if stress causes infertility. Multiple methods are known to treat infertility, but very few are known to address mental health issues that may lead to it. Studies were reviewed to see any correlation between infertility, current treatment practices, the associated effects on the individual's mental health, and possible psychological interventions that a medical healthcare provider may give.

Introduction

Infertility is the failure to achieve a pregnancy even after one year of regular unprotected intercourse. It is often mistaken as sterility. It affects millions of people in the childbearing age group (15-49 years). Recent data suggests that 15 percent of total couples of reproductive age are affected by infertility globally. One in four couples in a developing country is affected by infertility which can be primary or secondary.

- Primary infertility is the inability to conceive after 12 months of regular unprotected intercourse
- secondary infertility is the inability to conceive after the first successful pregnancy.

It is known to have significant consequences on a person due to the sense of losing control of one's own life and can cause confusion and anger to replace reasoning in a relationship. The highly demanding medication program one must undergo also strains relationships and can lead to further anxiety.

In males, infertility is commonly caused by problems in the ejection of semen, low sperm count, abnormal sperm morphology, or poor sperm motility. In females, the causes due to organic etiological factors such as endometriosis, hypothalamic dysfunction, and polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), among others, are commonly known. But we, through this review, want to focus on neuropsychiatric co-morbidities such as mixed anxiety depressive disorders and the role of mental health providers in dealing with the issue.

Infertility and its treatment can affect all aspects of people's lives, which can cause various psychological and emotional consequences and psychiatric disorders. Today couples seeking infertility treatment have drastically increased as they are aware

of available treatment options, and many women are starting a family later in favor of their higher education and career advancement. The condition of infertility needs to be considered an unplanned event rather than a significant impediment. Researchers have also studied the relationship between infertility, the gut-brain axis, the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, and infertility medications' role in developing neuropsychiatric disorders.

There is a need for patient-centered care at every step of counseling. The role of mental health care providers needs to be taken into consideration while talking about infertility treatment. The following table 1 outlines a few types of patient groups who experience infertility and methods to address it during counseling.

Type of Patient	Counseling Methods / Goals
Experiencing high distress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aid in the expression of emotions to help cope with treatment failure - Intercede to minimize distress
Pregnancy after infertility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable the transition from being infertile to being a pregnant patient while addressing emotions of ambivalence and disbelief about the pregnancy.
Sexuality of patient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systematically open-up discussion of sexual issues - Evaluate the significance and severity of any sexual problems for the couple and identify factors that may contribute to the problem (e.g., depression, side effects of medication)

Table 1: Showing type of patient and counseling methods with goals

Methods

The poster is a literature review. The goal is to scrutinize and evaluate the existing literature on the effects of infertility on the mental health of a couple. The research design method is an evidence-based rapid review. Standard literature and database searches with articles from 2010 - 2022 were implemented, gathering relevant material and assessing extracted information using keywords including infertility, infertility drugs, gut-brain axis, mental health, depression, and anxiety.

Discussion

Transition to parenthood is a moment of joy and pride for a couple. The psychological impact of infertility can devastate the infertile person and their partner. Infertility causes couples to experience a sense of loss of identity, feelings of helplessness, incompetence, insecurity, constant thoughts of being defective, and stigma from the society that ultimately, in many cases, becomes a reason for marital discord between couples. Reasons for psychological turmoil in infertile couples include the possibility of remarriage of a spouse, curiosity of significant others about the person's infertility, and humiliating behavior of others.

Stress, fear, depression, and anxiety are expected consequences of infertility. Stress and marital difficulties are often more in couples where the defect lies within the man. In general, women show higher levels of distress than their male partners. Research indicates the incidence of depression in infertile couples undergoing treatment is vastly greater than in fertile controls, with prevalence estimates of depression in the range of 15–54%. Anxiety is also higher in infertile couples than in the general population groups, where 8–28% of couples experiencing infertility have reported clinically significant generalized anxiety disorder and stress. Studies have also shown a correlation between infertility treatment and intestinal microflora which can decrease or inhibit the treatment outcomes and even slowly increase neuropsychiatric disorders in patients. A few examples are highlighted in table 2.

Figure 1 shows a diagrammatic representation of exogenous and endogenous factors that shape the intestinal microflora and play a role in significantly increasing the predisposition toward neuropsychiatric disorders.

Type of Drug	Observations
Clomiphene Citrate (CC)	Aggravated symptoms of irritability and mood swings
Combined Oral Contraception	Patients showed more depressive symptoms
Gonadotropin-releasing Agonists	Hormone A marked increase in depression-like symptoms and anxiety

Table 2: Observations seen in patients with type of drug used during Infertility treatment.

Conclusions

Globally, reproduction is one of the highest values in cultures and religions, and when childbearing seems impossible, many psychological effects set in. Assisted reproductive techniques act as a double-edged sword; while on the one hand, it fulfills a woman's dream of having children, on the other hand, it causes mental, social, financial, and legal concerns. Mental health professionals must meet the needs of infertile couples and the needs of the social system in which they live.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of exogenous and endogenous factors shaping the intestinal microflora and playing a role in significantly increasing the predisposition toward neuropsychiatric disorders

References

1. Deka, P. K., & Sarma, S. (2010). Psychological aspects of infertility | British Journal of Medical Practitioners. BJMP. Retrieved February 1, 2023, from <https://www.bjmp.org/content/psychological-aspects-infertility>
2. Doyle, M., & Carballedo, A. (2014). Infertility and mental health. *Advances in Psychiatric Treatment*, 20(5), 297–303. <https://doi.org/10.1192/apt.bp.112.010926>
3. Hasanpoor-Azghdy, S. B., Simbar, M., & Vedadhir, A. (2014). The emotional-psychological consequences of infertility among infertile women seeking treatment: Results of a qualitative study. *Iranian Journal of Reproductive Medicine*, 12(2), 131–138.
4. Simionescu, G., Ilie, O.-D., Ciobica, A., Doroftei, B., Maftei, R., Grab, D., McKenna, J., Dhunna, N., Mavroudis, I., & Anton, E. (2020). Mini-Review on the Possible Interconnections between the Gut-Brain Axis and the Infertility-Related Neuropsychiatric Comorbidities. *Brain Sciences*, 10(6), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci10060384>

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